

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF MEMBRANE TECHNOLOGY FOR THE SEPARATION OF C1–C4 GASES FROM CATALYTIC CRACKING PROCESSES

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Abstract

Membrane technology is emerging as a cost-effective alternative for C1–C4 gas separation. Membrane technology is characterized by low capital and operating costs, high energy efficiency, and automation capabilities. Cellulose acetate, polyimide, polysiloxane, and perfluorinated polymers are utilized for gas purification. Each polymer has a different permeability, selectivity, and chemical stability, and its resistance to plasticization is important in certain applications. Block copolymers (e.g., Pebax) provide a balance between hydrophilic and hydrophobic properties, providing high permeability and mechanical strength. Anodic alumina membranes have a nanochannel structure and are characterized by high permeability and tunable parameters, but their sensitivity limits their industrial application. Porous hollow-fiber polypropylene membranes are characterized by chemical stability and are manufactured by various manufacturing methods. Such membranes are widely used in gas drying, separation, and filtration processes.

Keywords: Catalytic cracking; absorption; absorbent; membrane method; methane; ethane; propane; butane.

Introduction

Membrane technology as an innovative approach in gas separation processes has been in the spotlight in recent years. Although membranes currently hold a limited market share in the separation of C1–C4 hydrocarbons, their application is steadily expanding. Given the complexity of absorption and adsorption methods and high energy requirements, the simplicity and efficiency of membrane devices are of great importance. Membrane technologies have the ability to simultaneously purify gas from both water vapor and acid components. Low capital costs, automation potential and flexible application areas increase the attractiveness of membranes. Materials such as cellulose acetate, polyimides, perfluorinated polymers and polysiloxanes act as the main membrane components in this field. Block copolymers, especially membranes based on Pebax, are considered promising in terms of selectivity and permeability. Porous membranes and anodized alumina-based structures are used to increase the efficiency of gas separation processes. Porous polymers such as polypropylene are widely used in membrane technologies. For this reason, membrane technologies play an important role in the future direction of Navtsiya gas processing.

Experimental part

Membrane separation technologies for C–Ca gases currently have a small market share (up to 10%). The main reasons for this are the complexity of the operation scheme of traditional absorption and adsorption methods and the complexity of membrane technologies for processing processes with volumes of hundreds and thousands of millions of tons. However, as the development of large gas fields is completed, and the demand for complex gas and oil and gas condensate fields increases, simple devices with high productivity and not requiring complex maintenance prove to be effec-

tive. Membrane technologies have the necessary potential for the creation of such devices. With the help of membranes, it is possible to simultaneously dry the gas from water vapor and higher hydrocarbons, as well as purify it from acidic components.

The main advantages of membrane technologies include:

- Low capital and operating costs
- Compactness, reliability and lightness
- Energy efficient, environmentally friendly, Possibility of full automation.

Membrane units can be integrated into conventional gas treatment processes, which allows for a 20–40% reduction in operating costs. MTR offers membrane roll cartridges based on the block copolymer Pebax 1074 in combination with absorption technologies. Currently, the membrane market is dominated by membranes based on cellulose acetate and polydimethylsiloxane [1]. Laboratory research is focused on the application of new polymers, such as polyether block polyamides (Pebax). The gas permeability and selectivity of membranes depend on the properties of the polymer, but in practice, due to the plasticization of polymers, the efficiency is 2–5 times lower than ideal. This problem is especially observed in raw gases with a high hydrocarbon content. The gas separation efficiency of membranes depends on the difference in partial pressures of the components in the waste gas and in the outlet stream. The mass transfer process is expressed by the following formula.

$$X_1 p_1 > X_2 p_2$$

Here X_1 , X_2 are the mole fractions of gas, and p_1 and p_2 are the pressures. The loss of methane during membrane purification can be 10% or more. To reduce losses, cycles with a second stage of purification are

used. In addition, before entering the membrane process, the gas must be cleaned of condensate and mechanical particles with a diameter of more than 3 microns, which creates additional capital and operating costs. An alternative direction of membrane technology that has been developing in recent years is the combination of membrane and absorption processes using membrane contactors. This method is based on the absorption of polluting components by liquid absorbents

through a membrane that acts as a separator of gas and liquid phases, provides a constant contact area and prevents the phases from penetrating into each other. Below, we consider in more detail the characteristics of membrane materials and membrane technologies for solving the main problems of natural and oil gas preparation.

Table 1

Gas transport parameters of membranes for water vapor removal

Polymer	$P(H_2O), m^3/m^2$	Separation factor (H ₂ O/N ₂)	Conditions
Cellulose acetate	0,036	190000	35C, 27atm
Pebax 1074	0,18	6060	30C, 1atm
Nafion 117	1,5	4,1.106	30C, 35C, 1atm
PDMS	0,16	38	30C, 350C, 1 atm

Non-porous polymers for gas purification and drying: Four main types of polymers are used for drying gases and removing acidic components: cellulose acetate, polyimides, siloxanes, and perfluoropolymers. Asymmetric membranes based on cellulose acetate were introduced into the industry in the early 1980s by Grace Membrane Systems, Separex, and Cynara, and currently account for 80% of the market. These membranes are widely used in offshore installations and for gas purification with high carbon dioxide content [2]. Cellulose acetate membranes are also capable of removing hydrogen sulfide with selectivities of up to 60 H₂S/CH₄ is able to separate. The permeability of cellulose acetate membranes is proportional to the degree of acidification of glycoside residues in the monomer unit of macromolecules. Bulky acyl groups prevent the dense packing of polymer chains. In addition, a decrease in the total proportion of OH groups in macro-

molecules leads to a decrease in the number of hydrogen bonds. As a result, the mobility and elasticity of polymer chains increase, and the permeability of membranes increases. The main disadvantage of cellulose acetate is its instability under the influence of water vapor, carbon dioxide and heavy hydrocarbons [3]. As a result of plasticization, the selectivity of separation decreases and the mechanical strength of the membranes weakens. Cellulose acetate is resistant to aromatic hydrocarbons such as benzene and xylene.

An alternative that offers greater resistance to water vapor is membranes based on polyimides. At the same time, polyimides are unstable to the effects of aromatic hydrocarbons, ammonia, and carbon dioxide. Increasing the plasticization resistance of polyimides has been achieved by chemical crosslinking [4;5], the introduction of inorganic fillers, and the production of composite membranes. Polyimide-based membranes are likely to have industrial demand.

Table 2

Gas transfer parameters of membranes for CO₂ removal

Polymer	$(CO_2), m^3/atm$	Separation factor (CO ₂ , CH ₄)	Pressure process	Selectivity ratio of gases (CH ₄ /CO ₂ /H ₂ S)%	CH ₄ losses during purification with up to 2% CO ₂	Source
Cellulose acetate	$8,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	38	10 atm	M(90.3/9.7/0)	2,67	[133]
Matrimid 5218 (stitched)	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	34	10 atm	M(95.92/4/800ppm)	3,21	[204]
Teflon AF2400	$6 \cdot 10^{-2}$	5,6	27 atm	M(88/10.5/1,5)	29	[88]
Hyllon AD40	$4,1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	16	27 atm	M(90/10/0)	11,7	[AvantaneOS 2206]
Cytop	$9,6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	18	27 atm	M(90/10/0)	7,6	[151]

Gas transport parameters of membranes for hydrogen sulfide removal

Polymer	P(H ₂ S)	Conversion coefficient H ₂ S/CH ₄	Pressure process	Gas mixture ratio (CH ₄ /CO ₂ /H ₂ S)%	CH ₄ losses while cleaning to ppm.	Source
Cellulose acetate	-	50	-	M(98\0\2)	16,29	[168]
Poly (ether urethane)PU3	271	58	10	M(70.8/27.9/1.3)	13,47	[24]
PDMS coated	28.86a	10,6	10	PES M(97.5/2.1/0.4)	51,5	[158]
Pebax 4011	-	70	26,66	M(95.79/4.12/870ppm)	7,41	[103]
PVBTAf	9.6c	1920	4,85	M(79.7/10/10.3)	0,53	[149]

Perfluoropolymers have high resistance to water, CO₂ and higher hydrocarbons.

Representatives of perfluoropolymers are Cytop, Teflon AF, Hyflon AD [5]. Due to the presence of high-energy C-F bonds, the macromolecules of perfluoropolymers are resistant to plasticization. For example, at pressures of up to 20 atm, plasticization of Teflon AF2400 and Hyflon AD80 polymers is not observed, while in cellulose acetate and polyimides this process begins at a pressure of 5-7 atm. Perfluoropolymer membranes for CO₂ removal under the trade name "Z-Top" are manufactured by Membrane Research, Inc. (MTR). Perfluoropolymers are suitable for cleaning low-quality gas with high water vapor and acid gases due to their hydrophobicity and low wettability by acid gases. Polysiloxanes are mainly used for the separation of C₁-C₄ hydrocarbons, drying of gases and removal of sulfur-containing components [6]. They have been widely used due to their high permeability and ability to form composite membranes with thin selective layers. There are three main approaches to increasing selectivity: modification of the chemical structure of polysiloxanes, creation of copolymers based on polysiloxanes, and incorporation of fillers into the polymer matrix.

Conclusion

Membrane technology is an effective and energy-efficient method for the separating of gas mixtures. The selection of membrane materials used in this process depends on their properties such as absorption, mechanical strength and chemical stability. The process of gas permeation through membranes is based on diffusion and dissolution mechanisms. In membrane technology, which determines the separation efficiency, different polymer and non-polymer-based materials are used to ensure the selective separation of various gases. This method, which is widely applied in fields such as petrochemical and ecology, requires less energy, consumption and simpler equipment compared to traditional gas separation methods. In recent years, experi-

ments have been conducted on new materials and nanocomposites to increase the efficiency of membranes. The development of membrane technology not only contributes to the solution of environmental problems, but also allows for the optimization of industrial processes. The continuous development of membrane technology will lead to the implementation of gas separation processes with higher efficiency and their widespread use in industrial sectors. Ultimately, the membrane method offers modern and effective solutions in the fields of gas processing and purification. Future scientific and technological achievements in this field will enable membrane systems to become more durable and high-performing.

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